

Morphology of Ruffini Endings and the Design of a Biomimetic Sensor

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Abstract. Ruffini endings have long been regarded as mechanoreceptors associated with slowly adapting type II (SA II) afferent fibers, a class of tactile afferents known to respond to sustained stretch deformation of the skin. Although the morphology and structural organization of Ruffini endings vary depending on the anatomical site in which they are found, they generally respond to tensile or stretch-related deformation of the surrounding tissue. In the present study, inspired by the site-dependent structural differences of Ruffini endings, we report a prototype strain-detection sensor embedded in an elastic medium that mimics these biological characteristics.

Keywords: Ruffini endings · Sensory Afferents · SA II · Sensors

1 Introduction

Among the afferent tactile sensory neurons, SA II units are known to respond to skin stretch. This has been reported not only in humans [1, 2] ([3] for a review), but also in neurophysiological recordings from hairy skin in cats and rabbits [4, 5], hairy skin in mice [6], and glabrous skin in monkeys [7], indicating that the existence of SA II units has been confirmed across multiple animal species. In addition, the sensation evoked by direct electrical stimulation of SA II has been described as a diffuse pressure sensation over a relatively wide area, which is qualitatively distinct from the localized pressure sensation evoked by electrical stimulation of SA I [8].

Based on findings from neurophysiology and skin anatomy, one of the earliest papers discussing the relationship between SA II and Ruffini endings was published by Chambers and Iggo in 1972 [5]. They first reported the existence of SA II units in hairy skin as distinct from SA I in a short report published in 1967 [9], and subsequently proposed the hypothesis that these units are connected to Ruffini endings. However, this perspective still remains open to verification even as of 2026. Reviews by Ginty and colleagues have repeatedly noted that, in mice, direct evidence that Ruffini endings necessarily correspond to, or can be equated with, SA II remains scarce and limited [10, 11].

This paper summarizes what is currently known about the morphology of Ruffini endings, which have been thought to be associated with SA II afferents, including findings from anatomical sites other than the skin. Based on this

overview, we discuss the potential of tactile sensors biomimetically modeled on Ruffini(-like) endings.

2 Types of Ruffini Endings Across Body Regions

2.1 Ruffini Endings in the Skin and the Joints

The morphology of Ruffini-like endings has been reported in several animal species. For example, in the hairy skin of the cat paw, Ruffini endings have been observed, and a confocal microscopy study confirmed that a Ruffini ending was located in the dermis and arranged so as to weave around hair follicles. In the glabrous skin of the human finger, there has also been a report describing the identification of a single Ruffini ending [12].

Given that receptive fields showing SA II responses are found in the human finger in non-negligible numbers [8], many authors have pointed out an apparent inconsistency: only a small number of Ruffini endings or Ruffini-like endings have been identified in the human finger. In other words, the association between Ruffini endings and SA II afferents should not be taken for granted.

More recently, Vega and colleagues examined a large number of human finger specimens for Ruffini endings using immunohistochemical methods. Although they confirmed the presence of Ruffini endings, the reported density was only 0.01–0.26 per mm^2 [13]. Thus, Ruffini endings are still found at a density that appears too low to support the notion that Ruffini endings are the end organs associated with SA II afferents.

When body regions other than the finger are considered, structures referred to as Ruffini endings have been identified in multiple anatomical locations. Mechanoreceptors in the cat knee joint have been described as Ruffini endings, and they show sustained neural firing as long as a mechanical stimulus of constant intensity is maintained [14]. Similar structures have also been reported in the human knee joint [15]. At present, afferents associated with Ruffini endings are thought to contribute to signaling that a joint is approaching the limit of joint extension.

2.2 Ruffini-Like Endings in the Periodontal Ligament of Teeth

Ruffini-like endings have also been described in the periodontal ligament. These terminal structures are arranged in close association with collagen fiber bundles in the periodontal connective tissue and are generally regarded as mechanoreceptive specializations that detect tension changes arising from minute tooth displacement and occlusal loading. Kannari (1990) characterized the morphology of Ruffini-like endings in the periodontal ligament and, using electron microscopy, examined their ultrastructural relationships with associated terminal Schwann cells as well as their morphological heterogeneity [16].

Maeda and colleagues reviewed several studies that elucidated the ultrastructure and distribution of Ruffini-like endings in the periodontal ligament,

Fig. 1. Braided sensor (a), embedded in an elastic gel (b), and sensor response (c).

and further organized previous findings regarding the plasticity, regeneration, and development of periodontal sensory innervation. Maeda et al. also pointed out that the development of Ruffini-like endings is closely linked to tooth eruption and the onset of occlusion, underscoring the significance of these terminal specializations as peripheral sensory apparatuses in the periodontal ligament [17]. In a later review, Maeda incorporated additional evidence on the mechanisms by which neurotrophic factors regulate the development and regeneration of Ruffini-like endings, further supporting the view that these endings contribute to mechanosensory transduction in the periodontal ligament.

In a recent study, Lee et al. (2025) showed that the mechanotransduction ion channel Piezo2 is expressed at least in the cell bodies of primary sensory neurons innervating the periodontal ligament, although it remains to be determined whether Piezo2 is specifically expressed in the afferent fibers associated with Ruffini-like endings themselves. Their findings nevertheless support the idea that primary sensory neurons innervating the periodontal ligament contribute to the transmission of both tactile and nociceptive information [18].

3 Implications for the Design of Biomimetic Tactile Sensors

Sensory afferents have been shown to respond to deformation and stretch of the periodontal ligament induced by forces applied to the tooth [19,20]. Ruffini(-like) endings in the periodontal ligament likely serve as mechanoreceptive end organs [17]. If Ruffini(-like) endings possess a structure closely associated with collagen fibers in the periodontal ligament and detect tissue stretch produced by minute tooth displacement, then such a mechanosensory architecture may provide useful guidance for designing sensor structures capable of detecting internal deformation in compliant bodies.

Based on this observation, a braided sensor was prototyped by combining conductive threads and elastic fibers (Fig. 1a). The braid was fabricated using three conductive threads (AGposs sewing thread 100/3, Mitsufuji) and five elastic fibers. The resulting braided sensor had a diameter of 1.3 mm, a length of 100 mm, and an electrical resistance of 5.2 $[\Omega]$. This braided sensor was embedded in an elastic gel and can be regarded as a variable resistor whose electrical resistance decreases with stretch (Fig. 1b). Stretch can be detected by measuring the temporal change in the voltage across a 100 $[\Omega]$ shunt resistor connected in series with the braided sensor (Fig. 1c).

In future work, we aim to use the proposed biomimetic sensor as a model system to clarify the functional role of Ruffini(-like) endings in vivo. We would like to engage both neurophysiologists and sensor engineers in discussing the development of this type of bio-inspired tactile sensor.

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